

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of 3-Substituted-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolin-2-ones

T. TILAKRAJ and SARVOTTAM Y. AMBEKAR*

Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of Mysore, Manasagangotri, Mysore-570 006

Manuscript received 24 December 1985, accepted 5 September 1986

3-Phenyl-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolin-2-ones and 3-acetamido-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolin-2-ones have been prepared by Perkin type condensation of 3-formyl-2-quinolones with sodium salt of phenylacetic acid and acetyl glycine, respectively. Mass spectral fragmentation pattern of these compounds have also been discussed.

In a general scheme to study the utility of 2-chloro-3-formylquinoline for the synthesis of new heterocyclic systems, we recently reported¹ synthesis of a series of 2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolin-2-ones. In continuation of our studies and in view of the anticoagulant², coronary constricting³ and optically brightening⁴ activities of 3-phenyl- and 3-amino-coumarins, a project of synthesising hitherto unreported 3-phenyl- and 3-acetamido-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolin-2-ones was undertaken. 3-Substituted-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolines are related to 3-substituted-coumarins in the sense that they are linear benzaza analogues of coumarins. 3-Formyl-2-quinolones (1a-g) obtained by the action of 4 M HCl on 2-chloro-3-formylquinolines¹, were subjected to Perkin reaction with sodium salt of phenylacetic acid and acetic anhydride to give 3-phenyl-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolin-2-ones (2a-g) in 70-80% yield; while condensation with acetyl glycine in presence of acetic anhydride and triethylamine gave 3-acetamido-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolin-2-ones (3a-f) in 30-40% yield (Scheme 1).

- a, R₁=R₂=R₃=H e; R₁=R₂=H, R₃=CH₃
 b; R₁=R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃ f; R₁=R₂=H, R₃=Cl
 c; R₁=R₂=OCH₃, R₃=H g, R₁=R₂=H, R₃=OH
 d; R₁=CH₃, R₂=R₃=H

Scheme 1

The ir spectra of pyranoquinolines (2a-g) showed two characteristic bands in the regions 1710-1740 and 1610-1620 cm⁻¹, which are assigned to the pyrone system. In case of pyranoquinolines (3a-f) additional bands due to amide carbonyl and amide-NH stretching frequencies were also seen at 1680 and 3320-3350 cm⁻¹, respectively. The pmr spectra of 2-substituted-pyranoquinolines resemble very much to that of 3-unsubstituted-pyranoquinolines¹ with the exception that 4H-proton which appeared as a doublet in the latter case appeared as a singlet in the region δ 8.4-9.1. Further, while pyranoquinolines (2a-g) exhibit an additional multiplet in the aromatic region due to the 3-phenyl protons, the pyranoquinolines (3a-f) exhibit two singlets due to amide NH and COCH₃ protons at δ 9.0 and 2.5, respectively.

The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of 3-phenylpyranoquinolines (2a-g) was very similar to that of 3-unsubstituted-pyranoquinolines as discussed in our earlier papers^{1,5,6}, with an additional peak at m/z 77 due to phenyl cation. However, the mass spectral fragmentation patterns of 3-acetamidopyranoquinolines (3a,b) were very characteristic. Molecular ion peak is not the base peak in both the cases, instead an ion corresponding to 3-amino-pyranoquinoline (4) is the base peak and is obtained through the loss of ketene CH₂=C=O from the molecular ion. Other significant fragmentations could be rationalised by considering the cation (4) either as an arylamine or as a substituted α-pyrone, as shown for (3a) in Scheme 2, and are in analogy with those observed for amines and pyrones⁷. Peaks involving fragmentation of methoxy group were observed in case of 3b.

Experimental

Ir spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer (nujol), pmr spectra in TFA on a Varian T-60 spectrometer using TMS as an

Scheme 2

internal standard, and mass spectra on a 707 OL instrument. Melting points are uncorrected.

3-Phenyl-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolin-2-ones (2a-g): General procedure: A mixture of 3-formyl-2-quinolone (1.73 g, 0.01 mol), freshly fused sodium phenylacetate (2.37 g, 0.16 mol) acetic anhydride (51 ml, 0.5 mol) was heated under reflux for 8 h at 170–180° in an oil-bath. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice (~100 g) with stirring and kept aside for 4–5 h. The pasty mass obtained after decantation was triturated with cold alcohol, and the resulting solid was filtered, washed with alcohol, dried, and recrystallised from acetic acid to yield 2a–g. The analytical, physical and spectral data are given in Table 1.

3-Acetamido-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinolin-2-one (3a–f): General procedure: A mixture of 3-formyl-2-quinolone (1 g, 0.0057 mol), acetylglycine (1.2 g, 0.01 mol), acetic anhydride (10 ml, 0.1 mol), triethylamine (5 ml) was heated under reflux for 24 h at 170–180° in an oil-bath. The mixture was then poured into crushed ice (~100 g) with stirring to get a brown solid. It was filtered, washed with water and dried. The dried product was triturated with acetic acid and filtered, and the resulting pale yellow solid was purified by recrystallising in excess of acetic acid to yield 3a–f. The analytical, physical and spectral data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Mol. wt.	m/s (% abundance)
2a	73	285	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ NO ₂	273	273(100), 245(30.84), 216(21.8), 202(12), 189(5.1), 136(4.2), 122(4.2), 108(5.12), 102(2.9), 94.5(3.84), 77(2.5), 63(2.1), 51(1.7)
2b	75	302	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ NO ₂	303	303(100), 288(2.1), 275(8.54), 260(18.8), 232(14.10), 216(1.28), 204(6.38), 189(1.28), 175(2.1), 163(0.42), 152(9.6), 137.6(5.5), 102.1(4.2), 94.5(1.2), 77(1.2), 51.0(0.85)
2c	75	240	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂	333	333(100), 318(4.27), 305(2.1), 290(5.5), 262.1(11.53), 247.1(1.7), 234.1(3.8), 219.1(7.6), 190(4.27), 166(8.4), 152.6(3.4), 131.1(1.28), 102(2.5), 102(0.38), 77(1.28), 51(0.42)
2d	73	280	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ NO ₂	287	287(100), 259(34.6), 231(4.7), 230(17.94), 215(5.98), 202(2.99), 176(0.42), 156(0.42), 143.5(9.6), 129.5(5.1), 115(5.2), 102(4.2), 77(2.56), 51(0.85)
2e	73	298	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ NO ₂	287	287(100), 259(32.05), 258(8.11), 230(14.95), 216(5.9), 202(2.99), 176(0.42), 157(0.42), 143(4.2), 102(4.27), 89.0(0.85), 77.0(2.98), 63(0.85), 51(1.28)
2f	60	310	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ ClNO ₂	307	307(33.76), 306(20.92), 307(100), 281(5.12), 279(22.2), 250.0(4.27), 216(17.94), 214(4.2), 189(2.09), 163(0.42), 153(4.27), 139.5(5.55), 125.5(1.28), 107.5(5.12), 94.5(2.49), 77.0(1.70), 51.0(0.854)
2g	60	287	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ NO ₂	287	287(100), 259(45.72), 231(6.40), 230.1(16.66), 216(5.12), 202.1(4.7), 176(0.42), 154(0.85), 143.6(3.41), 129.6(9.6), 115(4.7), 102.1(5.55), 88(2.0), 77.0(4.2), 63.0(1.10), 51(2.1)
3a	40	300	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	254	254(27.7), 214(1.8), 213(17.8), 212(100), 185(3.5), 184(23.6), 183(2.32), 167(1.6), 166(6.3), 156(6.3), 155(7.1), 128(14), 101(5), 102(5), 43(23.6)

(Table 1 contd.)

3b	40	340	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄	284	284(34.2), 343(15.6), 342(100), 228(3.3), 227(23), 214(11.2), 213(4), 199(11.6), 186(3.2), 171(6.3), 143(3.2), 142(4.1), 116(4.1), 43(23)
3c	35	327	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₅	314	
3d	35	280	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₅	268	
3e	35	345	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₅	268	
3f	30	348	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ O ₅	288	

* All compounds were analysed for C, H, N and the values found satisfactory.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. N. Rao, Department of Chemistry, University of Dublin, Dublin, for the microanalyses and mass spectra, Mr. B. Raju, I. I. Sc., Bangalore, for pmr spectra and U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (T. T.).

References

1. T. TILAKRAJ and S. Y. AMBEKAR, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 251.
2. L. H. SINGER and N. P. KONG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **88**, 5213.
3. I. C. BATHWAR and K. VENKATRAMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2420.
4. N. S. NARASIMHAN, R. S. MALI and M. V. BARVE, *Synthesis*, 1979, 906.
5. B. S. HOLLA and S. Y. AMBEKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, **18**, 187.
6. B. S. HOLLA and S. Y. AMBEKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 400.
7. H. BUBZIKIEWICZ, C. DJERRASSI and D. H. WILLIAMS, "Mass Spectrometry of Organic Compounds", Holden-Day, San Francisco, 1967, pp. 208, 322.